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Want to protect the environment? Advocate for women! Analysis of the impact of women on environmental spending

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Abstract

This paper investigates whether gender plays a role in public spending decisions in the environmental field. We consider a sample of 27 European Union countries from 2003 to 2022. Using Ordinary Least Square estimator, we show that a 1 percentage point increase in the share of women in government is associated with a 0.9 percent increase in public environmental spending. This result is robust to the addition of control variables, changes in the variables used to capture environmental spending, the use of alternative estimators, and are not country-specific. Heterogeneity analysis shows that women in senior positions have the largest impact on environmental spending. Contrary to intuition, the main result does not depend on the political party's orientation. It holds true regardless of when women participate in decision-making. When environmental expenditures are categorized, the presence of women increases spending on environmental R&D and water conservation, but reduces spending on waste management.

Keywords: • Fiscal policy • Environment spending • Women representation

JEL Classification: • E62 • Q58 • H61 • J16

1 Introduction

Contemporary environmental problems are numerous, from pollution to the loss of biodiversity. These include, but are not limited to, climate change, deforestation, water pollution and waste management. Macroeconomic environmental public policies aim to mitigate these environmental degradations. In particular, this translates into public spending targeted at these issues. The determinants of public spending are well-studied in the economic literature today. If we refer to [Lechevalier and Vigny \(2022\)](#), economic growth, the configuration of political systems, the democratization of societies, social demands, and the consequences of the increasing internalization of economies are the factors most often put forward. Of course, institutional complementarities can be added to these general factors when studying countries involved in economic integration, as well as the implications of the treaties establishing these trade or monetary unions.

Recent studies have examined whether the gender of policymakers affects public spending. They rely on empirical evidence from psychology or experimental economics suggesting that women are more risk-averse than their male counterparts ([Jianakoplos and Bernasek, 1998](#); [Bernasek and Shwiff, 2001](#); [Eckel and Grossman, 2008](#); [Croson and Gneezy, 2009](#); [Charness and Gneezy, 2012](#); [Beckmann and Menkhoff, 2008](#); [Bertrand, 2011](#); and [Filippin and Crosetto, 2016](#)). Most of these studies also reveal that women are less attracted to a competitive environment than men (see [Niederle and Vesterlund, 2007](#)). According to [Rubalcava et al. \(2009\)](#), women have a greater preference for the future than their male counterparts. Furthermore, [Horn et al. \(2022\)](#) show that women tend to be more altruistic than men.

Given special characteristics assumed for women, the question of gender's impact on decisions in the public sector should be considered. Women have different electoral

preferences than men. For example, [Funk and Gathmann \(2006\)](#) show that women are more likely to support spending on public goods such as the environment and public transport, while opposing defense spending and agricultural subsidies. Consequently, women's suffrage has a significant impact on the composition of public spending ([Aidt et al., 2006](#)). But what happens when women are in power?

At the local level, several studies show that the presence of women on elected councils influences the nature of public spending. For example, [Chattopadhyay and Duflo \(2004\)](#) and [Svaleryd \(2009\)](#) found that the presence of women on local councils led to increased spending on women's specific needs. Extending the analysis to the national level, women's influence on budget decisions remains evident and manifests itself at multiple levels. With regard to monetary policy, [Masciandaro et al. \(2023\)](#) show that central bank boards with a higher proportion of women tend to set higher interest rates for the same level of inflation. [Balvir and Vignoboul \(2024\)](#) point out that a higher proportion of women improves public budget management by increasing the countercyclicality of spending. [Fuchs and Richert \(2018\)](#) examine whether the characteristics of development ministers in Germany are associated with aid budgets and the quality of that aid. The results suggest that female ministers provide higher quality official development assistance (ODA). [Hessami and Fonseca \(2020\)](#) show that the increase in the number of women in power in developed countries does not affect total spending, but it does change policy choices. They tend to cut military spending ([Keneck-Massil et al., 2023](#)) in favor of health care ([Clayton and Zetterberg, 2018](#)).

Overall, these studies show, on the one hand, that gender plays a role in public spending decisions. On the other hand, some research suggests that women's suffrage may differ from men's in the composition of public spending. This article examines whether the presence of women in government has a specific impact on environmental spending.

The literature has questioned the link between gender and environmental concerns. [Glass et al. \(2016\)](#) investigate the impact women leaders have on the corporate environmental strategies of organizations. They show that firms characterized by gender-diverse leadership teams are more effective than other firms at pursuing environmentally friendly strategies. However, this article deals with decisions made by the private and not public sectors (see also [Jiang and Akbar, 2018](#)). According to [DiRienzo and Das \(2019\)](#), a more significant percentage of women in positions of political power improve environmental outcomes. However, this effect is generated by a reduction in corruption, and the study does not use time-series data, which limits the scope of results. [Lv et al. \(2020\)](#) show that female parliamentarians impact a country's environmental performance, provided a certain income threshold is reached. To account for this threshold, our article will focus on developed countries. It examines the direct relationship between women's presence in government and public environmental spending, taking into account the need for a time dimension.

To address this question, we consider 27 European Union member countries over 2003-2022. Using the Ordinary Least Square estimator, we highlight a relationship between the proportion of women in government and increased environmental spending. More precisely, environmental spending increases by 0.9% following a one-percentage-point increase in the share of women. Our main result is robust to the addition of control variables, changes in the measure of environmental spending, the use of alternative estimators, and a marginal change in our sample to ensure that some countries do not drive our effect. Heterogeneity analysis shows that women in senior positions have the largest impact on environmental spending. Contrary to intuition, this main result does not depend on the political party's orientation. It holds true regardless of when women participate in decision-making. When environmental expenditures are subcategorized, it appears that the presence of women increases expenditures on

environmental R&D and water conservation, but reduces expenditures on waste management. This article contributes to the understanding of gender impacts. One way to preserve the environment is to promote the inclusion of more women in leadership positions.

This article is structured as follows. Section 2 exposes the data used, and Section 3 presents the econometric analysis and results obtained. Section 4 performs a robustness analysis and Section 5 carries out a heterogeneity study. Section 6 gives a conclusion.

2 Data

To examine the relationship between women's participation in government and environmental spending, we focus on the 27 member countries of the European Union over the period 2003-2022. Data on women's participation in government are provided by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) database. Disaggregated data on public environmental expenditures are taken from Eurostat's Classification of Functions of Government (COFOG). The focus on European Union countries maximizes comparability between these countries, which share cultural and economic similarities. Although the European Union sets a general framework for economic and environmental policies, each member state retains a degree of budgetary autonomy in its spending. What's more, all EU member states are democracies, although they have different electoral systems. These two factors help to reduce the heterogeneity of our analysis.

2.1 Data on women's share

The data for our variable of interest, the proportion of women in government, come from the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) database. This database provides detailed, disaggregated information on the representation of women in the national governments of the 27 countries of the European Union on a quarterly basis for the period from 2003 to 2022. However, we cannot take full advantage of this time dimension because data on environmental expenditures are only available on an annual basis. Therefore, we have calculated annual averages of the female share by country over the four quarters of each year.

A notable advantage of the EIGE database for our study is its level of disaggregation. It distinguishes between ministers according to whether or not they hold a seat in the cabinet, with "senior" ministers holding a seat and "junior" ministers not holding a seat. The share of female senior (junior) ministers is calculated as the ratio of women with (without) a cabinet post to the total number of ministers with (without) a seat. This distinction helps us to assess relative levels of influence within the government. Similarly, it also classifies the share of ministers according to the BEIS typology: Basic, Economy, Infrastructure, Socio-cultural. For example, the share of women in economic positions is the ratio of the number of ministers with economic functions to the total number of ministers with economic functions. This facilitates the analysis of the differentiated impact of women according to their specific responsibilities.

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for the period 2003-2022. The average proportion of women ministers in European Union governments is 26%, with considerable heterogeneity within the sample (ranging from 0% to 58%). A more detailed analysis shows that the average proportion of women in non-cabinet positions ("junior"

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Share of Women Ministres	532	26.06	13.30	0.00	58.75
Share of Junior Women Ministres	496	18.89	17.94	0.00	83.35
Share of Senior Women Ministres	532	25.73	14.28	0.00	60.90
Share of Environmental Spending (% total)	540	0.99	0.74	-1.49	4.26
Share of Environmental Spending (% GDP)	540	0.32	0.29	-0.51	1.80

These statistics relate to the proportion of women in the national government. Junior means that the minister does not have a seat in the cabinet. For the share of women in junior or senior the ratio is made between the number of women and the total number of members in the same category, i.e. the share of junior women is calculated as the number of women in junior posts out of the total number of juniors in government.

Negative environmental expenditures may result from budget adjustments, reimbursements of unused funds, intergovernmental transfers, or the sale of environmental assets.

Source: Author's elaboration.

ministers) is lower than that of women in cabinet positions ("senior" ministers). Despite progress in improving women's representation, parity seems to be far from being achieved, even though women are on average more represented in the most important government positions. There are large disparities between countries, reflecting different national contexts in terms of women's participation in power.

Figure 1 illustrates this geographical heterogeneity by showing the average share of women in government in EU countries from 2003 to 2022. Some countries, notably the Nordic ones, have a relatively high proportion of women ministers, over 40%, while others, specifically in Eastern and Southern Europe, are well below this average. These differences highlight the influence of contextual and cultural factors on women's access to governmental responsibilities.

Figure 1: Share of women in EU governments

Average percentage of female ministers in each EU country, 2003-2022. Source: Authors' elaboration from EIGE database.

Figure 2 shows the evolution of women's representation in European governments over the period studied. There is a general upward trend, with an increase in female representation among ministers, especially those with a cabinet seat. However, the increase is less marked for women without a cabinet seat. This suggests that despite progress in integrating more women into high decision-making positions, significant obstacles remain in achieving equitable representation across all government functions.

In short, the descriptive statistics show that despite an overall improvement in women's representation, there are still marked differences between countries and between levels of responsibility within governments.

Figure 2: Trend in the proportion of women ministers in EU countries

Average share of women in EU countries over the period 2003-2022. Source: Author's elaboration from EIGE database.

2.2 Environmental expenditures

The data for the dependent variable, environmental expenditure, come from Eurostat's COFOG (Classification Of the Functions Of Government) database. This consolidated database, designed to maximize comparability between countries, provides a detailed overview of public expenditure in the Member States of the European Union, classified by function. One of the main advantages of this database is the breakdown of expenditure into specific sub-categories, which allows a more detailed analysis of government priorities. There are six subcategories of environmental expenditure: waste management, water waste management, pollution abatement, protection of biodiversity and landscape, R&D related to environmental protection and other environmental activities.

Table 1 shows that environmental expenditure represents on average 0.99% of total government expenditure and 0.32% of GDP for the period 2003-2022. However, there is considerable heterogeneity within our sample, reflecting the variability of

environmental priorities across EU countries and over time.

Figure 3: Average share of environmental expenditure in EU countries

Average share of environmental expenditure in EU countries over the period 2003-2022. Source: Author's elaboration from COFOG database.

Indeed, Figure 3 provides a comparison of countries according to the share of their total expenditure devoted to the environment. Surprisingly, several Eastern European countries devote on average more than 1.5% of their public expenditure to the environment, often exceeding the levels observed in other EU regions. This map also shows that there is no strict correlation between the share of women in government and environmental spending, reducing concerns about unobservable heterogeneity, possibly related to cultural or social factors that might influence these two variables.

Figure 4 highlights a general increase in environmental spending (in millions of euros) since 2003, with growth more than doubling over this period, despite a slight decline between 2014 and 2017. This growth reflects an increased awareness and commitment to environmental issues by EU governments, although spending levels fluctuate according to economic and political contexts. In terms of the ranking of

Figure 4: Total environmental expenditure for EU countries by year and subcategory

Years are shown on the y-axis. The x-axis shows the total amount of environmental expenditure in euros for the EU countries. We have plotted the six sub-categories of environmental expenditure in ascending order for each year. To make the graph easier to read, amounts displayed correctly within colored segments. The sum of the six gives the total environmental expenditure.

spending items, the two main categories over the period analysed are air pollution control and biodiversity conservation, which account for the majority of environmental spending. Environmental research and development (R&D) systematically ranks third or fourth, reflecting a constant but relatively low priority commitment to the development of new green technologies.

3 Model and main results

This section presents the econometric model used to analyze the impact of the proportion of women in government on environmental spending. The model specification is presented first, followed by the main results.

3.1 Model

Our paper focuses on the relationship between women’s share of government and environmental spending. To estimate this relationship, we use Equation 1:

$$\text{Environmental expenses}_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Women}_{i,t} + \beta_2 X_{i,t} + \mu_i + \rho_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

*Environmental expenses*_{*i,t*} is our dependent variable, measured as a percentage of total expenditure in country *i* in year *t*. The coefficient of interest, β_1 , is associated with our main variable, *Women*_{*i,t*}, which indicates the proportion of female ministers in the government of country *i* for year *t*. *X*_{*i,t*} includes a set of control variables in our model to capture factors that are likely to influence both environmental spending and the proportion of women in government, and to reduce omission bias. Table [A.1](#) gives more details on the variables and their sources.

We include the output gap to adjust our model for fluctuations in the business cycle that may affect environmental spending. From a Keynesian perspective, fiscal policy tends to be countercyclical. In times of recession, we might expect public spending, including environmental spending, to increase, while in times of economic expansion, it might decrease. However, if environmental spending is not perceived as essential to growth, the opposite effect could occur: a government facing a recession might choose to reallocate its resources by reducing environmental spending in favor of investments aimed directly at stimulating economic growth. What’s more, during a recession, the increase in spending induced by automatic stabilizers such as unemployment insurance or falling tax revenues could lead to a reduction in environmental spending, which might be seen as a lower priority.¹ We also include a crisis variable that may affect environmental expenditures by causing a reallocation of resources to

¹The examples of the "yellow vests" in France in 2019 or more recently the agricultural movements in EU countries clearly illustrate the difficult trade-off between environmental policies and economic and social demands.

the detriment of the environment.

We control for real GDP per capita as an indicator of a country's wealth. This variable is crucial to control for the effect of economic wealth on environmental spending, as wealthier countries tend to allocate more resources to social priorities, including the environment (Badulescu et al., 2019).

We take into account the lagged public debt in our model as it can have ambiguous effects on environmental spending. On the one hand, high public debt can constrain governments' fiscal capacity, thereby reducing global spending, including spending on the environment (Fodha and Seegmuller, 2014; Boly et al., 2023; Reinhart and Rogoff, 2010; Cottarelli, 2020). However, high public debt can also result from massive investments in low-carbon projects, clean energy initiatives, or environmental R&D activities that will primarily benefit future generations (Bénassy-Quéré et al., 2010).

We add trade openness (as a percentage of GDP), which can have opposite effects on environmental spending. On the one hand, trade openness may induce governments to strengthen their environmental policies to comply with international standards, especially if trade leads to an increase in carbon emissions through the economies of scale effect (Antweiler et al., 2001; Farhani et al., 2014). In this case, governments may need to increase their investment in environmental initiatives to mitigate the negative effects of trade. On the other hand, trade openness may also promote the adoption of cleaner technologies by facilitating technology exchange with trading partners, which could reduce the need for additional public spending on environmental issues (Dauda et al., 2021).

We then control for an index of the strength of fiscal rules, as strict fiscal rules may limit the flexibility of governments to increase environmental spending (Alesina et al., 1999; Hallerberg et al., 2007).

We also consider the structure of the population using the dependency ratio. An

older population can put pressure on public finances through higher social spending and may limit environmental spending (Sawadogo, 2020).

Finally, we take into account environmental taxes, an economic instrument that reflects the government's commitment to environmental protection and can also serve as a source of financing for environmental policies.²

We include a set of institutional variables that may affect both the share of environmental spending and the share of women in government.

First, the political ideology of the government may influence public spending, with left-wing governments tending to favor higher spending on social and environmental policies (Berdiev et al., 2012; Neumayer, 2003). In terms of women's representation, left-wing governments are also more likely to promote parity and increase the number of women in government (Braga and Scervini, 2017; Inglehart, 2003).

Second, government fragmentation, as measured by the distribution of party seats in government, may have ambiguous effects on environmental spending. On the one hand, a strong parliamentary majority may facilitate the adoption of ambitious policies, including environmental ones. However, in a fragmented government, compromises between different political forces can make the impact on environmental spending uncertain (Blais et al., 2010). The "common pool" theory suggests that coalitions within a government may increase public debt to satisfy various interests, including environmental spending, if some parties consider these issues a priority (Weingast et al., 1981; Kontopoulos and Perotti, 1999). On the other hand, the "theory of veto actors" suggests that government fragmentation can limit spending if certain members use their veto power, especially if these parties prioritize economic, industrial, or social issues over environmental ones.

²After testing for unit root, we take the first difference of the variables measuring GDP per capita, debt, trade openness, and environmental taxes.

Finally, election years can also affect public spending, including environmental spending, as governments often seek to satisfy interest groups or win votes during election periods (Nordhaus, 1975; Cukierman and Meltzer, 1986). Of course, election years also affect the composition of government.

We include country and year fixed effects to control for country-specific characteristics μ_i and time fixed effect ρ_t . These fixed effects neutralize the effects of factors that are constant over time within countries, as well as shocks common to all countries for each year, thus ensuring the robustness of our estimates. $\epsilon_{i,t}$ is the robust idiosyncratic error term to correct for heteroskedasticity.

3.2 Main results

We estimate Equation 1 with Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimator. Table 2 present our main results. Column (1) presents a basic structural model to assess the effect of the female share of government on environmental spending. In columns (2)- (8), we progressively add the control variables described above to test the sensitivity of our variable of interest. Finally, column (9) presents our baseline model with all the control variables.

We find that the coefficient associated with the share of women in government is positive and significant in all columns. One percentage point increase in the share of women in government is associated with an increase of 0.007 to 0.009 percentage points in the share of environmental spending in total spending. Although this effect may seem relatively small, it still corresponds to a 0.9% increase in environmental spending following a one-percentage-point increase in the share of women.³ Looking more closely at our baseline model in column (9), we can analyze the effects of the

³This result takes into account the coefficient in column 9 and a female share of 3%, which is the sample average, see Table 1.

control variables.

First, an increase in GDP per capita has a positive and significant effect on environmental spending. Environmental concerns tend to grow and are easier to finance as living standards rise.

We also observe that when government fragmentation is reduced (i.e., an increase in the variable), environmental spending increases. Thus, a government with a large majority, reflecting the majority composition in parliament, is more likely to pass an ambitious and substantial environmental budget. On the other hand, a more fragmented government may be paralyzed by internal opposition, limiting its ability to finance ambitious environmental initiatives.

The coefficient associated with fiscal rules is negative and significant. The negative effect of fiscal rules can be explained by a reallocation effect, whereby a government subject to restrictive rules is prevented from increasing the deficit and debt, leading it to make unfavorable trade-offs at the expense of the environment.

Surprisingly, crises seem to increase environmental spending. This may be explained by the adoption of Keynesian policies towards environmental initiatives and green investments, such as the US Green New Deal or the European Green Deal.

Finally, a high dependency ratio is associated with reduced environmental spending. Indeed, countries with an aging population face higher health and social protection (pension) costs, leading to a trade-off with environmental spending.

We find that the proportion of women in government is positively correlated with environmental spending. This effect can be explained by gender differences in preferences. Women tend to be more future-oriented and risk-averse, which may lead them, once in office, to influence budget decisions in favor of increased environmental spending. However, it is essential to test the robustness of our model to confirm this result.

Table 2: **Spending and share of women in government: base line results**

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Share of Women Ministres	0.007** (0.003)	0.008** (0.004)	0.007** (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)	0.009** (0.004)
Output Gap	-0.013 (0.014)	-0.013 (0.015)	-0.013 (0.014)	-0.013 (0.014)	-0.012 (0.014)	-0.013 (0.014)	-0.013 (0.014)	-0.015 (0.014)	-0.016 (0.015)
Lag Public Debt	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.006 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)
Lag Real GDP per capita	0.043** (0.020)	0.044** (0.020)	0.043** (0.020)	0.043** (0.019)	0.042** (0.019)	0.043** (0.020)	0.043** (0.019)	0.043** (0.020)	0.044** (0.019)
Trade Openness (% of GDP)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.004 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.004 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.004 (0.004)
Political Ideology		-0.028 (0.018)							-0.029 (0.018)
Seat share of parties in Gov			0.005** (0.002)						0.006** (0.002)
Year of Elections				-0.069 (0.043)					-0.054 (0.042)
Fiscal Rules Index					-0.081* (0.042)				-0.083* (0.043)
Crisis						0.085 (0.115)			0.201* (0.112)
Dependency Ratio							-0.017 (0.011)		-0.024** (0.011)
Environmental Taxes								-0.050 (0.073)	-0.059 (0.074)
Observations	403	403	403	403	403	403	403	403	403
Country FE	Yes								
Time FE	Yes								
R ²	0.7550	0.7565	0.7572	0.7566	0.7570	0.7550	0.7559	0.7556	0.7648

Notes: OLS estimations, controlling for country and time-fixed effects. The last column includes all of the additional controls simultaneously. Regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

4 Robustness

To test the robustness of our results, we perform a series of tests. First, we add control variables to limit omission bias, next we change our variables of interest, then we use alternative estimator (LSDVC) to account for the lagged endogenous variable. Finally we test the sensitivity of our results to the successive removal of countries from our sample.

4.1 Adding control variables

We include in Table 3 control variables that are likely to affect both our dependent variable and our variable of interest. This allows us to test the robustness of our model and limit omission bias.

In column (1), we include a variable describing the political system of the country, which takes the value of 1 for a parliamentary system and 0 for a presidential system. The associated coefficient is negative and significant, consistent with observations in the literature that presidential regimes are more inclined to provide public goods and allocate substantial environmental expenditures (De Mesquita et al., 2005; Bernauer and Koubi, 2009). This result may be explained by the greater ease with which presidential regimes can build a solid governing majority, as opposed to governments in parliamentary systems that often rely on coalitions.

In column (2), we add a variable related to political checks and balances to account for the distribution of power among decision-makers. Indeed, a rigorous system of checks and balances can be perceived as an implicit contract between the government and the electorate (Debrun and Kumar, 2009), thus promoting the defense of environmental initiatives could be more accurate. Conversely, greater fragmentation of power may complicate negotiations and coordination, making it more difficult to

pass a budget that favors environmental spending. However, the coefficient associated with this variable is not significant, suggesting that the effect of these mechanisms on environmental spending in our model is uncertain or limited.

We add the unemployment rate (as a percentage of the labor force) in column (3) to take into account both the business cycle and the budgetary priorities of governments. Indeed, in periods of high unemployment, automatic stabilizers lead to an increase in social spending, which may cause a budgetary reallocation to the detriment of environmental spending. However, the coefficient on this variable is insignificant.

In columns (4) and (5) we add variables for tax revenue and fiscal balance, both expressed as a percentage of GDP and lagged by one period. These variables allow us to control for the way environmental policies are financed, as they are the main sources of government funding. We find that the coefficients associated with these variables are positive and significant, suggesting that environmental policies are better financed when the government has greater financial resources, whether from a budget surplus or from tax revenues. It is important to note that the impact of the previous year's budget surplus on environmental spending is more pronounced than that of an increase in tax revenues. The implication of this observation is that excessive deficits, which require greater recourse to borrowing, could lead to a greater reduction in environmental spending than the increase in fiscal revenues.

Finally, column (6) gives us the results for all the control variables. Overall, we can see that the coefficient of our variable of interest, the proportion of women in government, remains positive, significant and of comparable magnitude for all columns, which indicates its robustness to the addition of control variables.

Table 3: **Environmental spending and share of women in government:
additional control variables**

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Share of Women Ministres	0.009** (0.004)	0.009** (0.004)	0.009** (0.004)	0.008** (0.004)	0.009** (0.004)	0.009** (0.004)
Output Gap	-0.016 (0.015)	-0.017 (0.015)	-0.024 (0.015)	-0.017 (0.015)	-0.016 (0.014)	-0.017 (0.015)
Lag Public Debt	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.008 (0.009)	0.010 (0.009)	0.018 (0.011)	0.019* (0.011)
Lag Real GDP per capita	0.044** (0.019)	0.044** (0.019)	0.044** (0.019)	0.049** (0.019)	0.046** (0.018)	0.050*** (0.019)
Trade Openness (% of GDP)	-0.004 (0.004)	-0.004 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.005 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.005 (0.004)
Political Ideology	-0.029 (0.018)	-0.029 (0.018)	-0.030 (0.018)	-0.031 (0.019)	-0.030* (0.018)	-0.029 (0.019)
Seat share of parties in Gov	0.006** (0.002)	0.006** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.005** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.005** (0.002)
Year of Elections	-0.054 (0.042)	-0.055 (0.042)	-0.051 (0.043)	-0.060 (0.042)	-0.038 (0.043)	-0.045 (0.043)
Fiscal Rules Index	-0.083* (0.043)	-0.083* (0.044)	-0.078* (0.042)	-0.068 (0.043)	-0.108** (0.044)	-0.097** (0.045)
Crisis	0.201* (0.112)	0.205* (0.112)	0.201* (0.113)	0.241** (0.116)	0.213* (0.110)	0.249** (0.114)
Dependency Ratio	-0.024** (0.011)	-0.024** (0.011)	-0.025** (0.011)	-0.028** (0.011)	-0.015 (0.011)	-0.020 (0.013)
Environmental Taxes	-0.059 (0.074)	-0.057 (0.074)	-0.060 (0.074)	-0.063 (0.074)	-0.056 (0.072)	-0.056 (0.072)
Political System	-0.383** (0.157)					-0.513*** (0.161)
Political Checks and Balances		-0.013 (0.030)				-0.012 (0.029)
Unemployment Rate			-0.011 (0.012)			-0.002 (0.014)
Lag Tax Revenue (% of GDP)				0.015*** (0.006)		0.014** (0.006)
Lag Fiscal Balance					0.036** (0.014)	0.036** (0.016)
Observations	403	402	403	395	403	394
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.7648	0.7648	0.7654	0.7689	0.7724	0.7764

Notes: OLS estimations, controlling for country and time-fixed effects. The last column includes all of the additional controls simultaneously. Regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 .

4.2 Change in measurement of environmental expenditures variable

The COFOG database provides detailed information on government expenditure at different levels of government. So far, we have used the share of environmental expenditure in total central government expenditure, since the decisions and the actions taken by ministers and especially by women in government mainly concern the central government budget. However, it is also possible to use the share of environmental expenditure for general government, i.e. the sum of environmental expenditure for all administrations (central and local). Indeed, while women in government may wish to increase environmental spending at the central level, they may also influence more local levels of government by transferring funds or promoting environmental initiatives that inspire local decision-makers. Column (1) of Table 4 presents the results when we replace the dependent variable in our baseline model with the share of environmental spending for the general government as a whole. The results show that neither the significance nor the magnitude of the coefficient associated with our variable of interest changes.

Column (2) presents a variant of the model using the share of central government environmental spending relative to GDP. The coefficient remains positive and significant, although at first glance its effect appears to be slightly reduced. However, interpreting the coefficient for an average environmental expenditure share of 0.32% of GDP (see Table 1), a one percentage point increase in the share of women in government leads to a 0.9% increase in the share of environmental expenditure in GDP. This effect is similar to the one previously observed in our baseline model.

Thus, the effect of the share of women in government on environmental spending appears to be robust to changes in the measurement of environmental spending.

Table 4: **Environmental spending and share of women in government:
change of the LHS variable**

	(1)	(2)
	Share for general Gov	Share in % of GDP
Share of Women Ministres	0.007** (0.003)	0.003** (0.001)
Output Gap	-0.019 (0.013)	-0.009* (0.005)
Lag Public Debt	0.001 (0.008)	0.002 (0.004)
Lag Real GDP per capita	0.031* (0.018)	0.011 (0.007)
Trade Openness (% of GDP)	-0.002 (0.004)	-0.001 (0.001)
Political Ideology	-0.026 (0.018)	-0.010 (0.006)
Seat share of parties in Gov	0.005** (0.002)	0.002** (0.001)
Year of Elections	-0.014 (0.039)	-0.015 (0.014)
Fiscal Rules Index	-0.048 (0.041)	-0.032** (0.014)
Crisis	0.112 (0.116)	0.049 (0.034)
Dependency Ratio	-0.035*** (0.010)	-0.003 (0.003)
Environmental Taxes	-0.004 (0.068)	-0.012 (0.023)
Observations	403	403
Country FE	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.7981	0.7962

Notes: OLS estimations, controlling for country and time-fixed effects. Regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 .

4.3 Change of estimators: LSDVC

Our dependent variable might be affected by past environmental expenditures. To address this concern, we chose to include a one-period lagged dependent variable in our model. However, the inclusion of a lagged dependent variable in a fixed effects model can introduce a Nickell bias (Nickell, 1981), which is particularly problematic when the number of time periods (T) is less than the number of cross-sectional observations (N). To avoid this bias, we change the estimator.

Table 5 shows the results of our benchmark model with the inclusion of the one-period lagged share of environmental expenditures. We use several estimation techniques to assess the robustness of our results. In columns (1) to (3) we use the Least Squares Dummy Variable Correction (LSDVC) estimator, with three different variants: Blundell-Bond (bb), Arellano-Bond (ab), and Anderson-Hsiao (ah) (Bruno, 2005). These variants are all designed to correct for the bias introduced by the inclusion of a lagged dependent variable, using different approaches to estimating dynamic effects in panel models.

The results show that the coefficient associated with women's participation in government remains positive, significant, and of a magnitude comparable to that observed in our baseline model with no lagged dependent variable. The effect of women in government on environmental spending is robust even after controlling for the influence of past spending. Including the lagged dependent variable captures the inertia of environmental spending while ensuring that the results are not biased by the correlation between the fixed effects and the lagged variable. These estimates strengthen the credibility of our findings, showing that the impact of women's participation in government is significant.

Table 5: **Environmental spending and share of women in government: change of estimator and lag LHS variable as control**

	(1)	(2)	(3)
	LSDVC (bb)	LSDVC (ab)	LSDVC (ah)
Lag share of environmental ex- pense	0.538*** (0.050)	0.488*** (0.053)	0.523*** (0.053)
Share of Women Ministres	0.007** (0.003)	0.006** (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)
Output Gap	-0.012* (0.007)	-0.012* (0.007)	-0.013* (0.007)
Lag Public Debt	0.010** (0.004)	0.010*** (0.004)	0.010** (0.004)
Lag Real GDP per capita growth	0.035*** (0.009)	0.034*** (0.008)	0.035*** (0.009)
Trade Openness (% of GDP)	0.000 (0.003)	0.000 (0.003)	0.001 (0.003)
Political Ideology	-0.017 (0.020)	-0.018 (0.019)	-0.018 (0.020)
Seat share of parties in Gov	0.005* (0.003)	0.005* (0.002)	0.005* (0.003)
Year of Elections	-0.015 (0.041)	-0.015 (0.038)	-0.015 (0.040)
Fiscal Rules Index	-0.019 (0.031)	-0.023 (0.029)	-0.018 (0.031)
Crisis	-0.081 (0.057)	-0.074 (0.053)	-0.085 (0.057)
Dependency Ratio	-0.004 (0.012)	-0.003 (0.011)	-0.004 (0.012)
Environmental Taxes	-0.090* (0.048)	-0.085* (0.044)	-0.093** (0.047)
Observations	403	403	403

Notes: Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 .

4.4 Check sensitivity

Given the large heterogeneity observed in the descriptive statistics, a potential problem could be the presence of outliers that may influence our results. The estimated coefficients could be amplified by certain countries with a high proportion of women, where environmental policies are particularly influenced by specific factors. To test the robustness of our results to this possibility, we successively excluded each country from the sample and re-estimated the model. Figure 5 shows the evolution of the estimated coefficient for the share of women in government in our baseline model after removing each country from the sample one at a time. Each country is denoted by the ID attributed in our dataset. The results show that the estimated coefficient for the variable of interest remains significant in all reduced samples, confirming the robustness of our results to the possible presence of outliers.

Overall, our results appear to be robust to the addition of control variables, changes in the measurement of our dependent variable, the use of different estimators, and the inclusion of lagged environmental expenditures to account for spending inertia, as well as to the exclusion of individual countries from our sample. It would be interesting to examine the cases in which the proportion of women in government affects environmental spending.

Figure 5: Coefficient of the share of women for each country dropped for the baseline result

The red line represents the value (on the Y-axis) of the share of women (the variable of interest) after individually dropping each country from the sample (country ID on the X-axis). The grey band covers the 90% confidence interval; the dashed line is the zero Y axis.

5 Heterogeneity

We highlighted a robust relationship between the proportion of women in government and environmental spending. In this section, we first examine the influence of the gender of decision-makers according to their responsibilities within the state. We also analyze the impact of the presence of women in government throughout the budget process. In addition, we study the role of the ruling party, which can influence both environmental spending and women's representation in government. Finally, we pro-

vide an in-depth analysis of the impact of gender on the distribution of environmental spending.

5.1 Gender impact by government position

As described in Section 3.1, the EIGE database enables us to distinguish the proportion of women according to their status in government, whether they hold a cabinet seat (senior ministers) or not (junior ministers). In addition, the BEIS classification provides information on the specific functions held by women. The EIGE database also provides us data on the gender of the head of government, the head of state, and the proportion of women in parliament. This information is essential to determine whether the effect of gender on environmental expenditure varies according to the position held, or whether it is limited to certain specific functions. On the same principle as for our initial variable of interest, we calculated an annual average for each category, then successively replaced our variable of interest by these in our model. Table 6 presents the results obtained for each of these functions.⁴

The results show that only the proportion of women with a cabinet seat has a significant impact on environmental spending. This observation is consistent with the idea that women in senior ministerial positions are better able to influence environmental budget decisions, given their direct access to key decision-making processes.

More surprisingly, neither the gender of the head of government or state nor the proportion of women in parliament had a significant effect on environmental spending. In addition, we found no significant effect of the proportion of women holding positions in the ministries of economy or infrastructure, even though these ministries often have

⁴We selected the economic and infrastructure functions from the BEIS classification because these are the two broad categories in which environmental issues are classified (i.e., Ministry of Energy, Ministry of the Sea, Ministry of Biodiversity, etc.). The names of the ministries and their classification between these two categories vary from one EU country to another.

environment-related responsibilities.

These findings suggest that the effect of gender on environmental spending is mainly collective and manifests itself across the government, particularly for women in senior positions. The impact seems to come from the budget process as a whole, where a general impetus in favor of environmental policies is given by an increased presence of women in government. This indicates that women’s influence on environmental policy is stronger when they participate collectively in decision-making, rather than when they occupy specific or isolated positions.

5.2 Gender effect along the budget process

As we have just seen, the effect of gender on environmental spending appears to be mainly due to the ability of female ministers to influence the national budget. However, it’s important to note that the budgeting process takes place over a period of time, and the impact of women’s presence in government can vary over the course of this process. What’s more, even after the budget is passed, it is common for it to be amended throughout the year.

To explore this temporal dimension, we have chosen to replace in our model the average annual share of women in government by the share of women for each quarter of year t , as well as for the last quarter of year $t - 1$, the key moment corresponding to the presentation and vote of the budget for year t . This approach also allows us to test the robustness of our variable of interest, since the share of women in government can fluctuate according to election years and ministerial reshuffles, which may occur independently of elections.

Table 7 shows the results of this analysis. We find that the coefficients associated with our variables of interest are all significant, positive, and of comparable

Table 6: **Environmental spending and share of women in government: according their functions and if they have a seat in the cabinet**

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Share of Women in Gov with a seat	0.006** (0.003)						
Share of Women in Gov without a seat		-0.000 (0.002)					
Share of Women in Gov Economic function			0.002 (0.002)				
Gender of the head of Gov				-0.000 (0.001)			
Gender of the head of State					0.000 (0.001)		
Share of Women in Parliament						0.006 (0.006)	
Share of Women in Gov infra function							-0.000 (0.002)
Output Gap	-0.017 (0.015)	-0.021 (0.015)	-0.016 (0.015)	-0.015 (0.015)	-0.018 (0.015)	-0.013 (0.014)	-0.016 (0.015)
Lag Public Debt	0.006 (0.008)	0.005 (0.008)	0.007 (0.009)	0.006 (0.009)	0.006 (0.009)	0.006 (0.008)	0.006 (0.008)
Lag Real GDP per capita	0.043** (0.019)	0.043** (0.020)	0.045** (0.019)	0.044** (0.019)	0.045** (0.020)	0.042** (0.020)	0.044** (0.019)
Trade Openness (% of GDP)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.005 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)
Political Ideology	-0.022 (0.017)	-0.016 (0.016)	-0.017 (0.016)	-0.014 (0.016)	-0.013 (0.017)	-0.016 (0.016)	-0.013 (0.016)
Seat share of parties in Gov	0.006** (0.002)	0.005** (0.002)	0.006** (0.002)	0.006** (0.002)	0.005** (0.002)	0.005** (0.002)	0.005** (0.002)
Year of Elections	-0.061 (0.042)	-0.050 (0.044)	-0.055 (0.043)	-0.058 (0.043)	-0.068 (0.044)	-0.063 (0.043)	-0.058 (0.043)
Fiscal Rules Index	-0.085** (0.043)	-0.089* (0.047)	-0.079* (0.042)	-0.082* (0.043)	-0.086* (0.045)	-0.084* (0.043)	-0.080* (0.044)
Crisis	0.216* (0.111)	0.330** (0.136)	0.228** (0.113)	0.228** (0.113)	0.248* (0.131)	0.224** (0.113)	0.246** (0.111)
Dependency Ratio	-0.025** (0.011)	-0.015 (0.013)	-0.023** (0.011)	-0.019 (0.012)	-0.017 (0.013)	-0.023** (0.011)	-0.023** (0.011)
Environmental Taxes	-0.055 (0.074)	-0.042 (0.075)	-0.056 (0.073)	-0.060 (0.075)	-0.062 (0.075)	-0.053 (0.074)	-0.060 (0.073)
Observations	403	384	403	401	391	403	405
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.7634	0.7624	0.7615	0.7591	0.7618	0.7611	0.7606

Notes: OLS estimations, controlling for country and time-fixed effects. Regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 .

magnitude, regardless of the quarter considered. These results highlight the consistency with which women in government appear to be committed to the environment through budgetary decisions, regardless of when they participate in the process.

5.3 The impact of political affiliation

Observed results could be the consequence of a spurious correlation between the proportion of women in government and environmental spending. Political party affiliation of the government could actually explain this relationship, as, for example, left-wing parties are traditionally more inclined to defend the environment and promote gender parity. This tendency could be reinforced by the partisan gender gap, which points out that women are more often elected in left-wing parties. This difference can be explained by both ideological factors - such as a stronger commitment to gender equality - and voters' biases against women. [Saltzer and McGrath \(2024\)](#) argue that Democratic voters are biased in favor of women, while Republicans tend to rely on traditional gender roles to evaluate candidates. Although we included a control variable for political ideology in our basic model, it remains difficult to determine whether the observed effect varies according to the party in power, especially since this variable is multinomial, making it difficult to interpret.

To explore this question further, we decide to re-estimate our baseline model in three different versions, introducing successively for the left, right, and center parties a variable from the CPDS database. This new variable measures the proportion of ministerial posts held by the party (left, right, and center), weighted by the number of days in office in a given year. It is included in two ways: first, as an interactive term with the share of women, to test the indirect effect of political affiliation via the share of women on environmental spending, and second, additively, to assess its

Table 7: **Environmental spending and share of women in government:
using quaterly measurement of the share of women**

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Share of Women in Gov Q1	0.007** (0.003)				
Share of Women in Gov Q2		0.007** (0.003)			
Share of Women in Gov Q3			0.006* (0.003)		
Share of Women in Gov Q4				0.009*** (0.003)	
Lag Share of Women in Gov Q4					0.006* (0.003)
Output Gap	-0.015 (0.015)	-0.016 (0.014)	-0.017 (0.015)	-0.017 (0.015)	-0.015 (0.015)
Lag Public Debt	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.008 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)
Lag Real GDP per capita	0.043** (0.019)	0.044** (0.019)	0.043** (0.019)	0.044** (0.019)	0.044** (0.019)
Trade Openness (% of GDP)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.004 (0.004)	-0.004 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)
Political Ideology	-0.026 (0.018)	-0.026 (0.018)	-0.025 (0.019)	-0.028 (0.017)	-0.025 (0.018)
Seat share of parties in Gov	0.006** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.005** (0.002)	0.006** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)
Year of Elections	-0.057 (0.042)	-0.058 (0.042)	-0.060 (0.044)	-0.051 (0.042)	-0.060 (0.043)
Fiscal Rules Index	-0.083* (0.043)	-0.083* (0.043)	-0.086* (0.045)	-0.081* (0.042)	-0.085* (0.044)
Crisis	0.218* (0.112)	0.203* (0.112)	0.194* (0.114)	0.196* (0.112)	0.225** (0.112)
Dependency Ratio	-0.024** (0.011)	-0.022** (0.011)	-0.016 (0.012)	-0.023** (0.011)	-0.023** (0.011)
Environmental Taxes	-0.058 (0.074)	-0.057 (0.074)	-0.079 (0.076)	-0.059 (0.073)	-0.059 (0.074)
Observations	403	403	376	403	402
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.7636	0.7635	0.7588	0.7656	0.7621

Notes: OLS estimations, controlling for country and time-fixed effects. Regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

direct effect.

The results presented in Table 8 show that neither the interaction variables nor the variables controlling for political affiliation are significant. On the other hand, the coefficient associated with the share of women in government remains positive and significant, indicating that the effect of women on environmental spending is independent of the political label of the government.

5.4 Women’s share and environmental expenditure subcategories

We have established a relationship between the proportion of women in government and environmental spending. This section investigates whether this increase in spending is evenly distributed across the various environmental spending categories. The COFOG database allows us to explore this question by dividing environmental expenditures into six subcategories: environmental R&D, waste management, biodiversity conservation, waste water management, air pollution control, and other environmental expenditures.

Table 9 shows the results obtained when we successively replace our dependent variable by each of these six subcategories, expressed as a percentage of total environmental expenditure. The results indicate that more women in government increases environmental R&D and water conservation but reduces spending on waste management. These results can be explained by women’s greater risk aversion and preference for future-oriented investments. Because women are thought to be more focused on sustainability and the conservation of natural resources, they are more likely to invest in low-carbon technologies and initiatives aimed at long-term environmental protection. Water management, a crucial issue in the face of global warming, could also

Table 8: **Environmental spending and share of women in government according to their political affiliation**

	(1)	(2)	(3)
Share of Women Ministres	0.009** (0.004)	0.007** (0.003)	0.009** (0.004)
Share of Women \times Left party	0.000 (0.000)		
Left party	-0.003 (0.003)		
Share of Women \times Right party		0.000 (0.000)	
Right party		-0.002 (0.002)	
Share of Women \times Center party			-0.000 (0.000)
Center party			0.003 (0.003)
Seat share of parties in Gov	0.006*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.006** (0.002)
Political Ideology	0.021 (0.058)	-0.057** (0.024)	-0.012 (0.020)
Output Gap	-0.016 (0.015)	-0.014 (0.015)	-0.016 (0.015)
Lag Public Debt	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)	0.007 (0.009)
Lag Real GDP per capita	0.044** (0.019)	0.041** (0.019)	0.042** (0.019)
Trade Openness (% of GDP)	-0.004 (0.004)	-0.004 (0.004)	-0.004 (0.004)
Year of Elections	-0.060 (0.045)	-0.057 (0.042)	-0.057 (0.042)
Fiscal Rules Index	-0.083* (0.044)	-0.081* (0.044)	-0.081* (0.042)
Crisis	0.198* (0.111)	0.224** (0.112)	0.227** (0.110)
Dependency Ratio	-0.025** (0.011)	-0.030*** (0.011)	-0.032*** (0.011)
Environmental Taxes	-0.063 (0.075)	-0.053 (0.076)	-0.056 (0.074)
Observations	403	403	403
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.7653	0.7670	0.7669

Notes: OLS estimations, controlling for country and time-fixed effects. Regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 .

benefit from this strategic orientation. The negative effect observed for waste management spending is more difficult to interpret. It is possible that this reflects a partial reallocation of funds in favor of R&D and water management, which could be perceived as long-term priorities.

According to our results, gender effect on environmental spending manifests itself in collective action at the government level, throughout the budget process, and regardless of the political party in power. Women in government seem to prioritize water conservation and, most importantly, environmental R&D.

6 Conclusion

The need to manage environmental problems raises the question of the most appropriate environmental policies. An indirect way of looking at this question is to analyze the determinants of public environmental spending. More specifically, this article investigates whether environmental expenditure depends on the gender of the public decision-maker. According to the literature, women are more risk-averse, less attracted to a competitive universe, have a higher discount rate and are more altruistic than their male counterparts. One wonders whether these features have any impact in terms of environmental preservation. The effect of gender has been addressed in the economic literature but more in the private sphere. This article sought to analyze whether increasing the share of women in government impacts environmental spending.

Considering a sample of 27 European Union countries from 2003 to 2022 and using the Ordinary Least Square estimator, we showed that increasing the share of women in government by one percentage point leads to a 0.9% increase in environmental spending. Robustness tests are carried out, and sensitivity analyses are performed to

Table 9: **Environmental spending and share of women in government: sub spending according the COFOG classification**

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	R&D	Waste	Biodiversity	Water	Air pollution	Others
Share of Women Ministres	0.128** (0.055)	-0.207** (0.095)	-0.104 (0.135)	0.235** (0.108)	-0.345 (0.495)	0.252 (0.307)
Output Gap	0.201 (0.146)	0.131 (0.642)	-0.216 (0.758)	-0.948* (0.566)	2.947 (3.346)	-2.434 (2.315)
Lag Public Debt	0.118 (0.105)	0.405* (0.217)	0.130 (0.254)	0.615*** (0.216)	-1.949* (1.070)	0.602 (0.656)
Lag Real GDP per capita	0.135 (0.220)	-0.761 (0.605)	0.557 (0.599)	1.192** (0.464)	-2.728 (2.564)	1.710 (1.679)
Trade Openness (% of GDP)	-0.084* (0.048)	0.105 (0.119)	0.043 (0.184)	0.017 (0.094)	-0.511 (0.806)	0.394 (0.513)
Political Ideology	-0.677*** (0.249)	-0.703 (0.798)	-0.646 (1.501)	-0.812 (0.530)	7.054 (6.773)	-4.291 (4.580)
Seat share of parties in Gov	0.024 (0.066)	0.058 (0.087)	0.198 (0.216)	0.072 (0.160)	-0.232 (0.337)	-0.095 (0.425)
Year of Elections	0.541 (0.760)	1.056 (1.835)	-1.543 (2.244)	-0.138 (1.443)	9.244 (9.270)	-8.126 (6.185)
Fiscal Rules Index	0.818 (0.728)	1.087 (1.394)	-3.008* (1.596)	-3.158* (1.819)	5.771 (5.562)	-1.734 (3.494)
Crisis	-1.726 (2.388)	-6.462 (5.496)	4.159 (4.151)	-5.533 (4.273)	23.473 (14.880)	-13.160 (9.207)
Dependency Ratio	0.656*** (0.156)	0.759* (0.421)	0.252 (0.428)	-0.590 (0.388)	-0.645 (1.040)	-0.549 (0.850)
Environmental Taxes	1.414** (0.693)	5.244 (3.369)	0.219 (2.129)	2.823 (5.279)	-7.929 (11.265)	-1.223 (5.511)
Observations	356	371	361	338	351	371
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.7796	0.5666	0.3778	0.4305	0.1731	0.2132

Notes: OLS estimations, controlling for country and time-fixed effects. Regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

show the robustness of our results. This main result applies especially to women in positions of responsibility and does not depend on the type of political party. Women, in particular, are driving an increase in public spending on environmental R&D and water management but reducing spending on waste management.

Promoting gender parity policies in the public sphere has an equity objective. Our results suggest that the consequences of these policies go beyond this and positively impact the environment. [Adams and Ragunathan \(2017\)](#) argue that if women had managed Lehman Brothers, the bank would not have gone bankrupt as women seem to be better crisis managers. This hopeful perspective raises the question: if more women were in power, could environmental problems be better managed?

As women are more risk-averse and have a higher discount rate, they value the future by spending more on environmental R&D. The result on waste management is more difficult to analyze. This work should be taken further, with a more detailed analysis of the various environmental items. It would also be interesting to look at women's specific characteristics, such as age or level of education, and the proportion of women in specific environmental positions in government and to consider more countries. But the analysis of these questions faces a sea of data. This emphasis on the need for further research engages the audience in the ongoing conversation about gender and environmental policy.

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Appendix

Table A.1: Sources and definitions of the variables

Variable	Definition	Source
Environmental expenditure	Environmental expenditure (GF05) of central government (S1311)/ general government (S13) as a percentage of total expenditure/GDP	COFOF, Eurostat
Women	Share of women within the executive power. Classification of functions according to the BEIS. Quarterly data	European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)
Output gap	Annual gap between the actual value and the potential value of the GDP	AMECO
Debt	Debt levels for the general government in % of GDP	Eurostat
Real GDP per capita	Gross domestic product divided by midyear population.	WDI, World Bank
Trade openness	Sum of exports and imports of goods and services measured as a share of gross domestic product.	WDI, World Bank
Political Ideologie	Cabinet composition (Schmidt-Index). Indicator from 1 [hegemony of right-wing (and centre) parties] to 5 [hegemony of social-democratic and other left parties].	Armingeon et al. (2022) , CPDS
Seat share of parties in Gov	Total government support: seat share of all parties in government. Weighted by the number of days in office in a given year.	Armingeon et al. (2022) , CPDS
Year of Legislative Election	Dummy variable for the years of election.	Armingeon et al. (2022) , CPDS
Fiscal Rules Index	Fiscal Rules Strength Index (FRSI)	Fiscal Rules Database, Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs
Dependency Ratio	Age dependency ratio is the ratio of dependents people younger than 15 or older than 64 to the working-age population—those ages 15-64.	WDI, World Bank
Environmental Taxes	An environmental tax is a tax on something that has a proven, specific negative impact on the environment, as a percentage of total government revenue.	Eurostat
Political System	Dummy variable: 1 for parliamentary, 0 for presidential	DPI2020, Database of Political Institution
Political Checks and Balances	Index ranking for 0 to 18	DPI2020, Database of Political Institution
Unemployment Rate	Unemployment refers to the share of the labor force that is without work but available for and seeking employment (in % of total labor force).	WDI, World Bank
Tax Revenue	Tax revenue refers to compulsory transfers to the central government for public purposes(in % of GDP).	WDI, World Bank
Fiscal Balance	in % of GDP.	Kose et al. (2022) , Fiscal Space Database